

Kinetics of Oxidation of *p*-Methoxyacetophenone by Selenium Dioxide in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium

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Kinetics of oxidation of ketones such as desoxybenzoin^{1,2}, 1,2-dibenzoyl ethane³, cyclic ketones⁴, acetylacetone⁵, acetophenone⁶ and of keto ester, ethylacetoacetate⁷, by selenium dioxide has been reported. In the case of acetophenones, it is reported that the electron-donating group in *para*-position of benzene ring accelerates the reaction rate, while the electron-attracting group retards the rate. However, oxidation of *p*-methoxyacetophenone under identical experimental conditions, shows that its reactivity towards the oxidising species is less than *p*-methylacetophenone, acetophenone and *p*-chloroacetophenone, though methoxy group in *para*-position of benzene ring is strongly electron-donating by resonance as indicated by its σ_p^+ value (-0.778). This prompted us to investigate the kinetics of oxidation of *p*-methoxyacetophenone by selenium dioxide in order to find the cause of low reactivity of this substrate towards oxidising species and thereby suggest a suitable explanation. We, therefore, report here the kinetics of oxidation of *p*-methoxyacetophenone by selenium dioxide in aqueous acetic acid.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of *p*-methoxyacetophenone by selenium dioxide has been investigated in 70% (v/v) acetic acid-water. The order of reaction with respect to selenium dioxide is one. The reaction is also first order in substrate (Table 1). Sulphuric acid catalyses the reaction (Table 2). The acid catalysis in selenium dioxide oxidation^{1-8,8} is attributed to the oxidising species, $H_3SeO_3^+$ and $AcH_2SeO_3^+$, which are more reactive than H_2SeO_3 and $AcHSeO_2$ respectively.

The primary salt effect of added neutral salt K_2SO_4 , on the rate of reaction is negligible in dilute solutions. This suggests that at least one of the

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS
Temp = 338 K, HOAc : Water = 70 : 30 (v/v)

Effect of selenium dioxide concn :					
[<i>p</i> -methoxyacetophenone] = 0.80M					
$10^3 [SeO_2] M$	4.0	8.0	10.0	12.0	16.0
$10^3 k s^{-1}$	4.32	4.30	4.23	4.20	4.20
Effect of <i>p</i> -Methoxyacetophenone concn :					
[SeO_2] = 0.01M					
[<i>p</i> -MAP]M	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	0.80
$10^3 k s^{-1}$	1.01	2.08	3.14	4.23	4.23
$10^3 k [p-MAP]$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	5.05	5.20	5.23	5.29	5.29

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SULPHURIC ACID CONCENTRATION
[SeO_2] = 0.01M, [*p*-Methoxyacetophenone] = 0.50M, Temp. = 338 K, HOAc : Water = 70 : 30 (v/v)

$[H_2SO_4] M$	0.00	0.025	0.05	0.10	0.25
$10^3 k s^{-1}$	2.50	6.00	7.60	9.30	13.7

reacting species in the rate-determining step is a neutral molecule⁹.

The effect of varying percentage of acetic acid on the rate of reaction has been studied. It is observed that the increase in the percentage of acetic acid in the reaction mixture increases the rate (Table 3). Plot of $\log k$ vs $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ is linear with positive slope, suggesting the reaction to be dipole-dipole¹⁰ type.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF PERCENTAGE OF ACETIC ACID ON REACTION RATE

[SeO_2] = 0.01M, [<i>p</i> -Methoxyacetophenone] = 0.80M, Temp. = 338 K					
HOAc : Water (v/v)	65 : 35	70 : 30	75 : 25	80 : 20	85 : 15
$10^3 k s^{-1}$	3.38	4.23	5.50	7.59	10.02

The calculated values of activation parameters are $\Delta H^* = 67.4$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S^* = -131.3$ J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta G^* = 111.7$ kJ mol⁻¹ respectively.

The reactivity of *p*-methoxyacetophenone towards oxidising species is found to be the least among acetophenone, *p*-methylacetophenone, *p*-chloroacetophenone (Table 4).

TABLE 4—REACTIVITY OF ACETOPHENONES

[SeO_2] = 0.01M, [Substrate] = 0.80M, HOAc : Water = 70 : 30 (v/v)				
Substrate (Acetophenones)	$10^3 k_s^a$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹
H	8.69 ± 0.14	70.4	-113	109.61 ± 0.68
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	10.45 ± 0.10	72.7	-109	109.46 ± 0.85
<i>p</i> -Cl	6.78 ± 0.13	69.9	-121	110.63 ± 0.88
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	5.29 ± 0.12	67.4	-131	111.73 ± 0.58

^aValue at 338 K.

It should be noted that the *p*-methoxy group is strongly electron-donating by resonance but is not quite as strong as the σ_p^+ value (-0.778) predicts. It is presumably because of its interaction with the solvent, that is, methoxy group hydrogen bonds strongly to the solvent as in (a) and (b). This

results in an increase in the value of σ_p^\ddagger for this group and thereby lowers the reactivity of methoxy group.

Another possible cause of deviation of *p*-methoxy group may be ascribed to the formation of dypnone as acetophenones are known to undergo acid-catalysed condensation to form these. With *p*-methoxyacetophenone this should occur readily. But the uv spectra of acetophenones in acetic acid solvent do not give the absorption band (*K*-band) in 215–250 nm region, which is characterised by enones¹¹. The observed uv absorption is in the region 240–260 nm for acetophenone, while for *p*-methoxyacetophenone it is in the region 250–290 nm. It is reported¹¹ that acetophenone gives band at 240 nm. The bathochromic shift may be attributed to the solvent and substitution effects. Thus the deviation observed in the reactivity of *p*-methoxyacetophenone may not be due to the formation of its enones. Hence it may be concluded that the low reactivity of *p*-methoxyacetophenone is due to the interaction of *p*-methoxy group with the solvent, that is, it hydrogen bonds strongly to the solvent.

Perusal of Table 4 reveals that oxidation of acetophenones by selenium dioxide is entropy-controlled. The free energy of activation is nearly of the same order as for the other studied acetophenones, which suggests that the oxidation of *p*-methoxyacetophenone by selenium dioxide follows the same mechanistic path.

It is reported⁶ that the electrophilic attack of the oxidising species of selenium dioxide occurs directly on keto form of acetophenones (1) in a slow step to form an enol selenite ester (2). The latter rearranges in fast steps to a selenium(II) keto ester (3) and finally to phenylglyoxals (4) as shown in (Scheme 1), where ϕ stands for C_6H_5 , *p*- $CH_3C_6H_4$, *p*- ClC_6H_4 and *p*- $CH_3OC_6H_4$ for acetophenone, *p*-methylacetophenone, *p*-chloroacetophenone and *p*-methoxyacetophenone respectively.

Experimental

Selenium dioxide (Loba), *p*-methoxyacetophenone (Fluka, A.G.) and acetic acid (G.R.) were used. Other chemicals were of A.R. grade. A 0.1 *M*

Scheme 1

selenium dioxide solution was prepared by dissolving selenium dioxide in water and standardised iodometrically. The reaction rate was determined by estimating the unreacted selenium dioxide at known intervals of time by iodimetric method⁴.

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